

Breastfeeding – The Environmentally Friendly and Ideal Method of Infant Feeding

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Abstract

Breastfeeding has been proven scientifically to offer many health benefits for infants and mothers, as well as potential economic and environmental benefits for communities. The current breastfeeding rate in Nigeria has remained low and diarrhoea have remained the second biggest killer of children in Nigeria owing to consumption of contaminated water and unhygienic practices in food preparation. This review aims to provide a broad overview of existing findings on breastfeeding, highlighting its benefits, its role in maternal and child health; and also identify factors across several dimensions that influence breastfeeding outcomes. The review was designed to identify studies on breastfeeding, prelacteal feeding, infant formula feeding and diarrhoea diseases. Results shows that in low and middle-income countries, about half of all diarrhoea episodes and a third of respiratory infections could be avoided by breastfeeding. However, millions of children are failing to receive the full benefits provided by breastfeeding. Infant formula production and consumption is one of the major threats to breastfeeding and to the environment. Mothers go for the alternative formula feeding of artificial baby milk which has been implicated in the death of one and a half million babies every year and ill health. Breastfeeding produces zero waste in comparison to infant formula. In contrast to breastmilk, artificial baby milk production pollutes the land, air, and water and uses up natural resources. Currently, breastfeeding promotion focuses on encouraging women to breastfeed without adequate antenatal education and counselling, supportive environment at home and work places. In conclusion, breastmilk remains the only readily available, safe and environmentally friendly source of infant feeding especially for the first six months of an infant life. It is recommended that in promoting, protecting and supporting breastfeeding at the level of family, community and work place; there must be political will and commitment by the government. The aggressive marketing of infant formula must also be controlled from advertisement to sales and regulations enforced.

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Keywords: Breastfeeding benefits, infant formula, environment and breastfeeding support.

1. Introduction

Breastfeeding, also called nursing, is the process of feeding a mother's breast milk to her infant, usually directly from the breast. WHO defined exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) as an infant receiving only breast milk without food, drink, and water. Scientifically, there are evidences that the mother's milk is the best food for optimal health of the new-born infant. Mother's milk alone provides all the nutrients necessary for a baby's physical and mental development for the first six months, with the added benefit of natural immunity against numerous diseases ([World Health Organization, 2009](#)). New estimates produced by the Lancet Series reveal that increasing breastfeeding to

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near-universal levels for infants and young children could save over 800,000 children's lives a year worldwide, an equivalent to 13% of all deaths in children under two, and prevent an extra 20,000 deaths from breast cancer every year (The Lancet, 2016). Despite the awareness being created by various governments and non-governmental organizations on benefits of EBF, its practice remains lower than the globally recommended standard especially in developing countries (Adeyinka et al., 2008). As shown in Figure 1, according to the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey in 2018 (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019), exclusive breastfeeding rate in Nigeria is no measure to that of the global rate of 41%. EBF rate in Nigeria were 13%, 17%, 29% in 2008, 2013 and 2018, respectively, with just 16% increase from 2008 (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF Macro, 2009; National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF International, 2014; National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019). These are far lower compare to the 50% global target by the World Health Assembly for 2025 (UNICEF, WHO, 2018). Optimal breastfeeding is the most cost-effective child survival strategy (Sankar et al., 2015), and has the potential to reduce under-five mortality by 13% in developing countries (UNICEF and World Health Organisation (WHO), 2010). Breastfeeding has been identified as and recommended to be the preferred feeding method for infants, and it has been shown to be one of the most important contributors to infant and maternal health (UNICEF and World Health Organisation (WHO), 2010). Optimal breastfeeding consists of early initiation within an hour of birth, exclusive breastfeeding from birth to 6 months of life and breastfeeding up to 2 years of age or beyond (UNICEF, 2019). This review aims to provide a broad overview of existing findings on breastfeeding, highlighting its benefits, its role in maternal and child health; and identify factors across several dimensions that influence breastfeeding outcomes.

2. Benefits of Breastfeeding

Provide all the nutrients necessary for a baby's physical and mental development for the first six months. Breastfeeding provides adequate water for hydration and protects an infant against infection and allergy. It provides added benefit of natural immunity against numerous diseases (UNICEF, 2010). Breastfed babies experience fewer incidents of ear infections, allergies, diarrhoea, bacterial meningitis and sudden death syndrome (León-Cava et al., 2002). Breastfed babies are sick less often than bottle-fed babies as they grow older; therefore, parents will spend less time caring for their sick children (World Health Organization, 2002). Breastfeeding also increases intelligence, and might protect against obesity and diabetes in later life (The Lancet, 2016). Overall, breastfeeding duration and exclusive breastfeeding reduces the risk of hospitalization for infectious diseases (Duijts et al., 2010). For mothers, longer-duration breastfeeding reduces the risks of breast cancer and ovarian cancer (Cramer, 2012). It promotes bonding and development, improves maternal health by reducing postpartum bleeding may lower the risk of breast and ovarian cancers (World Health Organization, 2002).

3. Breastfeeding Initiation and Pre-lacteal Feeding

Increasing the rate at which an infant is feed breastmilk could save over 800,000 children's lives The Lancet (2016). Five million deaths in children younger than five years were reported globally in 2015 and almost half (46%) of these occurred in the neonatal period (Smith et al., 2017). The initiation of breastfeeding early after child birth and practice of exclusive breastfeeding during the first month have been associated with reduced neonatal mortality and morbidity (Khan et al., 2015). Early breastfeeding initiation (EBFI) is recommended within the first hour following parturition as a simple strategy in enhancing neonatal health and survival (UNICEF and World Health Organisation (WHO), 2010; Hailemariam et al., 2015). As shown in Figure 1, early breastfeeding initiation for infant is at 42% (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019), compare to 33% in 2013 (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF International, 2014), and 38% in 2008 (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF Macro, 2009). There is an increase and an equal to the global data of 42% (UNICEF, WHO, 2018), and this might be a contribution to the decreasing of burden of infant mortality and morbidity. Breastfeeding is a culturally determined behaviour. The cultural practices of infant feeding vary from culture to culture and relate to time of initiation of breastfeeding, frequency of breastfeeding, and duration of breastfeeding among others. Culture refers to values, beliefs, norms and practices of a particular group, which are learned, shared and which guide attitudes, decisions and actions in a patterned way (Uchendu et al., 2009). Progress in the adoption of exclusive breastfeeding

had been slow in Nigeria and the reason might be partly that breastfeeding is an embodied practice that is strongly rooted in culture. This gives rise to the use of water with medicinal herbs or roots, that are usually employed in the treatment of abdominal colic experienced by infants and this affects exclusive breastfeeding practice, indicating the existence of a strong underlying restraining factor which could be traced to cultural practices (Ibe et al., 2017). The cultural practice of water, medicinal herbs and infant to infants either to handle a crying baby or to quench child's thirst or to relieve abdominal pain, poses greater risks to the child health as the child digestive system is not well matured to start digesting other foods. Particularly, in developing countries where there is limited access to clean and safe water, infants are also at high risk of infections, malnutrition, and death. Researchers in the Netherlands found dangerous bacteria, which can cause meningitis and sepsis, in 52.5 percent of the formula samples they cultured from 35 countries (Muytjens et al., 1988; Norberg et al., 2012).

Figure 1. Prevalence of Breastfeeding in Nigeria (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF Macro, 2009; National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF International, 2014; National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019).

4. Breastfeeding and Diarrhoea

In the rural area of the developing countries, their main sources of water are rivers, streams and wells, which are prone to contamination from open defecation, chicken droppings or cattle excrement and abandoned refuse, the main risk factor for diarrheal disease, especially for the children (Harris et al., 2017; Njuguna, 2016; Gizaw et al., 2018). Diarrhoea is more common among infants who did not start breastfeeding within one hour immediately after birth and are introduced to water or any form of pre-lacteal feeding (World Health Organization, 2009; Gedefaw and Berhe, 2015). According to the National Demographic Health Survey, 2019, clean water is a basic need for human life. The urban dwellers has a higher level of accessibility to improved source of drinking water (74%), in relation to the their rural dwellers counterparts who had 42% accessibility as shown in Figure 2. Only 26.3% rural dwellers had water in their premises, with 65.8% travelling 30 minutes or less to obtain clean and safe drinking water as shown in Figure 3 (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019). Formula feeds have less essential ingredients than breastmilk (Ben-Joseph, 2018). Furthermore, it may contain pollution as the water that is used to dissolve the powder may be contaminated (Akhtar et al., 2017; Dabeka et al., 2011; Winkler et al., 2015), which increases the incidence and severity of infectious diseases, primarily acute diarrhoea (World Health Organization, 2009; Gedefaw and Berhe, 2015) which cause the death of about 88% of children and these is attributed to unsafe water (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2015). Report from National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF (2019) shows that the incidence of diarrhoea in Nigeria has increased from 10% both in 2008 and 2013 respectively, to 13% in 2018 (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019) as shown in Figure 4.

5. Breastfeeding, Infant Formula and Environment

Health outcomes in developed countries differ substantially for mothers and infants who formula feed compared with those who breastfeed. Annually, every new born is a potential additional to the infant formula market. Infant

Figure 2. Source of Drinking Water in Nigeria (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019).

Figure 3. Time to obtain drinking water (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019).

formula or baby milk are product of a lot of industrial processes which has an impact on the environment, contributing to global warming and climate change through environmental damage, degradation and pollution (Linnecar et al., 2014). Linnecar et al. (2014) further emphasis that a lot of waste materials is been produced from packaging and non-biodegradable plastics which accumulate in landfill sites, or are burned in open fires or in incinerators which produce toxic emissions, especially when incinerators are over-burdened by waste. Breastmilk is environmentally sustainable (UNICEF, 2013) and a valuable natural resource, which does not make use of any raw material but naturally sourced with zero waste in comparison to formula feeding as there is no waste from packaging, or from plastic feeding bottles or plastic water bottles. Breastfeeding keeps the environment unharmed and has zero water footprint (Linnecar et al., 2014).

6. Breastfeeding and GMO

Genetically modified (GM) foods are foods derived from organisms whose genetic material (DNA) has been modified in a way that does not occur naturally, and these genes may come from bacteria, viruses, insects, animals or even humans (WHO, 2015). Genetically modified ingredients may be present in soy-based infant formula (Walker, 2015) with traces of anti-nutrients such as phytate, aluminium and phytoestrogens that might cause unanticipated effects (National Toxicology Program, 2010). American Academy of Environmental Medicine reports that several studies indicates serious health risks associated with genetically modified (GM) foods causing infertility, immune

Figure 4. Diarrhoea in Under-five children (National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF Macro, 2009; National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF International, 2014; National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019).

problems, accelerated aging, faulty insulin regulation changes in major organs and the gastrointestinal system are issues of concern that have been raised with GMO products (American Academy of Environmental Medicine, 2009). Children are three to four times more prone to allergies than adults and are at highest risk of death from a food allergy (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2013). Infants below two years old have the highest incidence of reactions, especially to new allergens encountered in the diet (Steinman, 2010). Breast milk have been the sole source of nutrition for a long time for an infant and have been an issue of concern for the immature gut of the infant. The debate has been that genetically engineering foods is a relatively new practice, little is known about the long-term effects and safety.

Human milk is not skimmed, processed, pasteurised, homogenised, packaged, stored, transported, repackaged, dried, reconstituted, sterilised or wasted. More important to many people nowadays, it is not genetically modified (Francis and Mulford, 2000). Breastmilk is a renewable natural resource produced and delivered without contamination and pollution to the consumer and the environment. The use of GM has raised public concerns on the use of the principle of 'substantial equivalence', and the possible effects of GM foods on human nutrition and allergic responses. New born infants can be spared from the concerned effect raised about GM by encouraging breastfeeding mothers to breastfeed optimally.

7. Support for breastfeeding

Breastfeeding rates are suboptimal internationally, and many infants are not receiving any breast milk at all by six months of age (Forster et al., 2019). Breastfeeding is a skill that must be learnt by mother and child for good breastfeeding outcome. However, first-time mothers are inexperienced and lack knowledge about breastfeeding, which may hinder the effectiveness and efficiency of breastfeeding. Mothers need to have skills on the latching of infants to the breast, sustaining and maintaining lactation, handling breastfeeding challenges.

Factors that have contributed in undermining breastfeeding are lack of understanding and education of mothers and health care providers. Other contributory factors are inadequate support for mothers at birth, after hospital discharge and at the community level. Employment policies that don't support and encourage breastfeeding mothers and aggressive marketing of infant formula are also contributory factors. Some mothers on the first day of birth dropped the idea of breastfeeding owing to lack of support from health care providers or other stakeholders which negatively influence their breastfeeding decision. A Cochrane review found that both professional and lay support were effective in prolonging breastfeeding, with professional support being the most effective of the two (Britton et al., 2007).

For continuous breastfeeding mothers need support in hospital during birth and home after discharge. The influence of the grandmothers proved to be a determining factor for the continuity of breastfeeding or for early weaning.

Grandmothers are important as to the transmission of knowledge, wisdom, and experiences related to infant feeding (Moreira and ER, 2013).

Father support has been demonstrated empirically to have a strong influence on a mother's decision to initiate and continue breastfeeding (Britton et al., 2007). In Rempel and Rempel (2011) study whilst all fathers felt the mother had the final say regarding the decision to, and stop, breastfeeding a number of fathers were still involved in decisions about whether and how long to breast feed.

8. Conclusion

To guarantee our babies' health depends on having clean air, clean water, safe food and safe environment. Breast-milk as a product has been endorsed to be the safest, uncontaminated and environmental friendly, with the product consumed without waste that could contribute to environmental disaster. Support for breastfeeding at the household, community and organizational level is key in the raising the prevalence of breastfeeding practices of mother.

9. Recommendation

Ensuring child health in the first 1000 days of life will be achieved through the promotion, protection, and support of breastfeeding at the level of the household, community, workplace and health care. Increased awareness about the benefit of breastfeeding and government commitment at the policy level is equally important.

References

- Adeyinka, T., Ajibola, F., Oyesoji, A., 2008. A hospital-based assessment of breast-feeding behaviour and practices among nursing mothers in Nigeria and Ghana. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition* 7, 165–171.
- Akhtar, S., Shahzad, M.A., Yoo, S.H., Ismail, A., Hameed, A., Ismail, T., Riaz, M., 2017. Determination of aflatoxin M1 and heavy metals in infant formula milk brands available in Pakistani markets. *Korean J Food Sci Anim Resour* 37, 79–86.
- American Academy of Environmental Medicine, 2009. Genetically Modified Organisms. Technical Report. American Academy of Environmental Medicine. URL: <https://www.aaemonline.org/gmo.php>.
- Ben-Joseph, E.P., 2018. Breastfeeding vs. Formula Feeding (for Parents). Technical Report. Nemours KidsHealth. URL: <https://kidshealth.org/en/parents/breast-bottle-feeding.html>.
- Britton, C., McCormick, F.M., Renfrew, M.J., Wade, A., King, S.E., 2007. Support for breastfeeding mothers. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* Issue 1. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD001141.pub3.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2013. Voluntary guidelines for managing food allergies in schools and early care and education programs. Technical Report. US Department of Health and Human Services. Washington, D.C., USA.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2015. Diarrhea: Common illness, global killer. Technical Report. US Department of Health and Human Services.
- Cramer, D.W., 2012. The epidemiology of endometrial and ovarian cancer. *Hematol Oncol Clin North Am.* 26, 1–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hoc.2011.10.009>.
- Dabeka, R., Fouquet, A., Belisle, S., Turcotte, S., 2011. Lead, cadmium and aluminum in Canadian infant formulae, oral electrolytes and glucose solutions. *Food Addit Contam Part A Chem Anal Control Expo Risk Assess* 28, 744–753.
- Duijts, L., Jaddoe, V.W., Hofman, A. and Moll, H.A., 2010. Prolonged and exclusive breastfeeding reduces the risk of infectious diseases in infancy. *Pediatrics* 126, e18–e25.
- Forster, D.A., McLardie-Hore, F.E., McLachlan, H.L., Davey, M.A., Grimes, H.A., Dennis, C.L., ..., Shafiei, T., 2019. Proactive Peer (Mother-to-Mother) Breastfeeding Support by Telephone (Ringin up About Breastfeeding Early [RUBY]): A Multicentre, Unblinded, Randomised Controlled Trial. *EclinicalMedicine* 8, 20–28. URL: http://whqlibdoc.who.int/publications/2004/9241591544_eng.pdf.
- Francis, S., Mulford, C., 2000. The Milk of Human Kindness: a global fact sheet on the economic value of breastfeeding. International Women Count Network - Crossroads Books.
- Gedefaw, M., Berhe, R., 2015. Determinates of childhood pneumonia and diarrhea with special emphasis to exclusive breastfeeding in North Achefer District, Northwest Ethiopia: A case control. *Open J Epidemiol.* 5, 107–112.
- Gizaw, Z., Adane, T., Azanaw, J., Addisu, A., Haile, D., 2018. Childhood intestinal parasitic infection and sanitation predictors in rural Dembiya, Northwest Ethiopia. *Environ Health Prev Med* 23. doi:10.1186/s12199-018-0714-3.
- Hailemariam, T.W., Adeba, E., Sufa, A., 2015. Predictors of Early Breastfeeding Initiation among Mothers of Children below 24 months. *Biomed. Central* 15, 1076.
- Harris, M., Alzua, M.L., Osbert, N., Pickering, A., 2017. Community-level sanitation coverage more strongly associated with child growth and household drinking water quality than access to a private toilet in rural Mali. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 51, 7219–7227.
- Ibe, S.N.O., Obasi, O., Nwoke, E.A., Nwifo, C.R., Ebrim, C.I.C., et al., 2017. Cultural Practices on Infant Feeding and Nursing-Mothers' Adoption of Exclusive Breastfeeding Practice in Imo State Nigeria. *MOJ Public Health* 5, 00141. doi:10.15406/mojph.2017.05.00141.

- Khan, J., Vesel, L., Bahl, R., Martinez, J.C., 2015. Timing of Breastfeeding Initiation and Exclusivity of Breastfeeding During the First Month of Life: Effects on Neonatal Mortality and Morbidity—A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Matern Child Health J* 19, 468–479. doi:10.1007/s10995-014-1526-8.
- León-Cava, N., Lutter, C., Ross, J., Martin, L., 2002. Quantifying the benefits of breastfeeding: a summary of the evidence. Pan American Health Organization, Washington DC 3.
- Linnecar, A., Gupta, A., Dadhich, J., Bidla, N., 2014. Formula for disaster: weighing the impact of formula feeding vs breastfeeding on environment. BPNI/IBFAN Asia .
- Moreira, M.A., ER, N., 2013. Intersectionality family, generation and breastfeeding. *Rev Kairós Gerontol* 15, 191–208.
- Muytjens, H.L., Roelofs-Willemse, H.A.N.N.I.E., Jaspar, G.H., 1988. Quality of powdered substitutes for breast milk with regard to members of the family Enterobacteriaceae. *Journal of clinical microbiology* 26, 743–746.
- National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF, 2019. Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018. Technical Report. NPC and ICF. Abuja, Nigeria, and Rockville, Maryland, USA.
- National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF International, 2014. Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2013. Technical Report. NPC and ICF International. Abuja, Nigeria, and Rockville, Maryland, USA.
- National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF Macro, 2009. Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2008. Technical Report. National Population Commission and ICF Macro. Abuja, Nigeria.
- National Toxicology Program, 2010. NTP-CERHR monograph on Soy Infant Formula. Technical Report 23. NTP CERHR MON.
- Njuguna, J., 2016. Effect of eliminating open defecation on diarrhoeal morbidity: an ecological study of Nyando and Nambale sub-counties, Kenya. *BMC Public Health* 16, 712. doi:10.1186/s12889-016-3421-2.
- Norberg, S., Stanton, C., Ross, R.P., Hill, C., Fitzgerald, G.F., Cotter, P.D., 2012. Cronobacter spp. in powdered infant formula. *Journal of food protection* 75, 607–620.
- Rempel, L.A., Rempel, J.K., 2011. The breastfeeding team: the role of involved fathers in the breastfeeding family. *Journal of Human Lactation* 27, 115–121.
- Sankar, M.J., Sinha, B., Chowdhury, R., Bhandari, N., Taneja, S., Martinez, J., Bahl, R., 2015. Optimal breastfeeding practices and infant and child mortality: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Acta paediatrica* 104.
- Smith, E., Hurt, L., Chowdhury, R., Sinha, B., Fawzi, W., Edmond, K., et al., 2017. Delayed breastfeeding initiation and infant survival: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS ONE* 12, e0180722. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0180722>.
- Steinman, H., 2010. Nutritional implications of food allergies. *South African Journal of Clinical Nutrition* 23, 37–41.
- The Lancet, 2016. Increasing breastfeeding worldwide could prevent over 800,000 child deaths every year - Baby Friendly Initiative. URL: <https://www.unicef.org.uk/babyfriendly/lancet-increasing-breastfeeding-worldwide-prevent-800000-child-deaths-every-year/>.
- Uchendu, U., Ikefuna, A.N., Emodi, I.J., 2009. Factors associated with exclusive breastfeeding among mothers seen at the University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital. *South African Journal of Child Health* 3, 14–19.
- UNICEF, 2010. Improving exclusive breastfeeding practices by using communication for development in Infant and Young Child Feeding programmes. Technical Report 16. UNICEF. New York.
- UNICEF, 2013. Breastfeeding is the cheapest and most effective life-saver in history Media Centre. Technical Report. UNICEF. URL: http://www.unicef.org/eapro/media_21214.html.
- UNICEF, 2019. Nutrition: breastfeeding. Technical Report. UNICEF. New York. URL: https://www.unicef.org/nutrition/index_24824.html.
- UNICEF and World Health Organisation (WHO), 2010. Indicators for Assessing Infant and Young Child Feeding Practices. Part 3: Country profiles. UNICEF and WHO. Geneva.
- UNICEF, WHO, 2018. Capture the Moment – Early initiation of breastfeeding: The best start for every newborn. Technical Report. UNICEF. New York.
- Walker, M., 2015. Formula Supplementation of Breastfed Infants: Helpful or Hazardous? *ICAN: Infant, Child, & Adolescent Nutrition* 7, 198–207.
- WHO, 2015. Food, Genetically modified. URL: https://www.who.int/topics/food_genetically_modified/en/.
- Winkler, B., Aulenbach, J., Meyer, T., Wiegner, A., Eylich, M., Schlegel, P.G., Wiegner, V., 2015. Formula-feeding is associated with shift towards Th1 cytokines. *Eur J Nutr*. 54, 29–138.
- World Health Organization, 2002. Essential Newborn Care and Breastfeeding. Technical Report. WHO. Geneva. URL: [Availableat:https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/107481/e79227.pdf;jsessionid=...](https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/107481/e79227.pdf;jsessionid=...)
- World Health Organization, 2009. Infant and Young Child Feeding (IYCF): Model Chapter for Textbooks for Medical Students and Allied Health Professionals 2009. Technical Report. WHO. Geneva. URL: http://www.wpro.who.int/nutrition_wpr/publications/infantchildfeeding.pdf.